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Realization of Industry 4.0 in Objective Identification and Smart Sensing with OpenCV and NI Vision

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ABSTRACT

We developed a project to achieve the realization of Industry 4.0 in objective identification and smart sense through network communication in an echo system of production lines. The machine vision was carried out with OpenCV and NI Vision. With robotic-assisted Uarm Metal, measurements of the specific physical properties for the identified objects were implemented with embedded microcontroller utilities. Finally, the test results were uploaded to the public cloud server, ThingSpeak. The connection on the practical mechanical system and the platform of information interaction demonstrated the paradigm of the cyber-physical system.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Physics and Engineering Education

Keywords: objective identification, smart sense, internet of things, industry 4.0

INTRODUCTION

The fast development in network communication and cloud computing in the past decade has boosted the evolution of computer technology, programming design, and information management to a whole new stage of application and service, and has stimulated the dream of the realization of the Internet of things (IoT) [1]. Benefiting from the worldwide population of wireless remote control, sensing devices, and advanced measurement and display instruments, innovations in the IoT related technologies and market demand continue to expand and are setting the standards of future technology. Meanwhile, the integration of embedded systems and computer languages has turned the production and manufacture into new types with better efficiencies—smart sensing, together with custom manufacturing, have established the key feature of Industry 4.0 (I4) [2]. Furthermore, with the development of the cyber-physical system [3], the connection between virtual and real worlds has been established, bringing with it IoT environments with vivid objective communications, artificial intelligence, and human-computer interactions.

As the current industrial production still faces many critical challenges in smart automation because of the increasing complexity and the need for flexibility [4], the requirements that include portability, interoperability, and reliability have been identified as prerequisite for future industry. Among various strategies, machine vision provides innovative solutions to reduce difficulties in the direction of industrial automation [5]. A variety of applications of vision systems provide evidence of the practices and effects of optical inspection. In general, the processes of machine vision include image acquisition, image processing, feature extraction, and identification judgment. To achieve precise identification in complex or highly-sensitive environments, such as face recognition, a feature-based or figure-based algorithm would be considered. As a result, reliable identification depends not only on high-resolution image acquisition; the efficiency of the recognition software matters as well.

Figure 1. The flow of optical identification, object diversion, and back-end test. The production line and measurement platform are constructed from LEGO modules.

In this work, we report the development of a project in cooperation with Yulon Motor Group to achieve the realization of I4 in objective identification and smart sensing through network communication on an echo system of production lines. The project was implemented in the two-month summer vacation after a four-month lecture course that introduced the kernel, the aim, and the practice of I4. Before proceeding, students have to submit the proposal and the budget to demonstrate their idea, schedule and processes to design the project with the classroom equipment by applying the previously learned domain knowledge. In doing the project, students were guided to construct, review, and revise their blue chart. This greatly helped build a clear picture for what to do, how to do, and flow debug, and then greatly increase the probability for students without engineering background to complete the project of image identification in time.

In terms of the software structures, the image identification was implemented parallel with two schemes, OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision) and NI Vision (National Instrument Vision). OpenCV is open source software with powerful libraries for image processing, and supports C, C++, Python, and JAVA. In contrast, based on the graphic-based interface, LabVIEW, NI Vision was designed as commercial software. In this work, we designed programs for dynamic image acquisition, identification and analysis with Python and LabVIEW, and compared the identification results and specific advantages of the two algorithms.

In terms of the hardware structures, we constructed and controlled the conveyor and mechanical system with LEGO EV3 and servo motors. After image identification, the object diversion to the back-end physical-test platform was performed with robotic-assisted Uarm Metal. The utilization of the ATmega168 chip and Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment) helped easily realize the simultaneous control of three-axial motors and Bluetooth sensors, and completed the diversion. In this project, we further designed a measurement platform for three physical properties including notch depth, battery capacity, and strain. The control of the mechanical system of the platform was achieved with Arduino Uno combining pressure and voltage sensors. The measurement of the strain in terms of optical pulse deviation from fiber gratings provides an alternative for fragmental detection. Finally, the test results were uploaded to the public cloud server, ThingSpeak, via the ESP-8266 Wi-Fi module to supply the service for information interaction and feedback.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Based on the LEGO EV3 dynamic modules, we developed a project of objective identification and established a physical-test platform on an industrial production line to simulate the object diversion and quality management in the smart manufacturing. The experimental setup is demonstrated in Fig.1.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

With a CCD/webcam to capture the image of objects (tires, batteries, and engine gaskets) that are carried randomly on the conveyor belt dynamically controlled by servo motors (Fig.1 right & Fig. 2a), we use two computer vision software packages (OpenCV and NI Vision) for the recognition of object characteristics. The item information of passed objects is transmitted to the robotic arm, Uarm Metal, by the bluetooth module, while the defective objects are disposed of in the recycling area. The three-axis motor and electromagnet are controlled via the ATmega chipset in the Uarm, by which the objects will be suspended and carried to the correct backend platform for property characterization, including tread depth, battery power, temperature, and pressure. We use Arduino and different sensors for measurement, and the test results are uploaded to the cloud server, ThingSpeak (Fig. 2b) by Wi-Fi. This web page is a public platform, where both the engineers and customers can freely check the dynamic production line process, and send their opinions back via the embedded Google form. The complete experimental procedure is depicted in the flow chart below (Fig. 3).

Figure 2a. Driving and speed control of servo motors for the conveyor.

Figure 3b. The current theme of ThingSpeak.

Figure 3. The flow chart of smart manufacture, from identification to quality testing and to the public cloud.

RECOGNITION THEORY

[1] OpenCV—Python

The OpenCV supplied machine vision is completed via (i) background photo shooting with the webcam or CCD, (ii) grey-scale transformation, (iii) dynamic image acquisition and background extraction, (iv) threshold setting and noise filtering, (v) configuration positioning, and (vi) Matchtemplate supplied database comparison.

In the edge control and threshold setting, the Canny Edge Method [6] also known as the optimal detector, is adopted. With the Canny algorithm, the image recognition through Gaussian filtering, Sobel test, non-maximum suppression, and two-threshold hysteresis would be expected to satisfy a low error rate, good localization, and minimal response.

Template Matching is a method for searching and positioning of a template image in a larger image. In the convolution process, the template image slides over the input image and compares the template and patch of input image under the template image. By using TM_CCoeff, it returns a greyscale image of global maximum (R) according to

$$R(x, y) = \sum_{x', y'} (T'(x', y') \cdot I'(x + x', y + y')), \quad (1)$$

where

$$T'(x', y') = T(x', y') - 1/(w \cdot h) \cdot \sum_{x'', y''} T(x'', y''), \quad (2)$$

$$I'(x + x', y + y') = I(x + x', y + y') - 1/(w \cdot h) \cdot \sum_{x'', y''} I(x + x'', y + y''), \quad (3)$$

record the correlation of the neighbourhood of the pixel between the template T in the size of $w \cdot h$ and the object image I .

[2] NI Vision—LabVIEW

The NI Vision supplied machine vision is completed via (i) localhost setting and dynamic vision acquisition, (ii) threshold setting, (iii) look-up table generating, (iv) grey morphology, and (v) OCR/OVR conversion.

After image acquisition, we set the threshold for color-grey conversion and set the pixel number in the grey scales by means of bilevel thresholding. To enhance the contrast and the lightness of the image, we then generate a look-up table to renew the grey scales. Further, we apply Greyscale Morphology to trim the configuration of the object in terms of masks of erosion, dilation, opening, and closing [7]. Finally, we apply OCR (Optical Character Recognition) and OCV (Optical Character Verification) to work out analog-digital conversion for computer recognition. The identification program in the LabVIEW structure is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Implementation of objective identification by graphic-based interface of LabVIEW.

RESULTS

Fig. 5 and 6 display the flow charts of objective identification with text-based OpenCV and graphic-based NI Vision, respectively. In both schemes, the recognition proceeds following the rule: image acquisition, image processing for background extraction, grey-scale modulation for noise elimination and contrast enhancement, and finally database comparison. Essentially, the threshold setting is critical in the determination of the limitation and efficacy of grey-scale modulation to shape and configure the image. For database comparison, we adopt surface inspection to implement the characteristic identification. To avoid reflection smear, a strong color

contrast is suggested to clearly distinguish between the characteristic symbol and the image body.

In this project, the recognition is precisely achieved in both schemes. However, compared with the commercial suite, it is truly a challenge for the beginners to understand the recognition theory and build the programs with the open source. But on the other hand, the use of OpenCV takes the advantages to easily connect with the embedded system while the realization of remote control via LabVIEW-for-Arduino becomes a new task, too.

Figure 5. The flow chart of objective identification with OpenCV.

Figure 6. The flow chart of objective identification with NI Vision.

Fig. 7 left demonstrates the grey-scale images of the objects and characteristic surfaces that serve as templates of the database. The image identification is to calculate the correlation between adjacent pixels of the template and the object via the convolution process. As blue lines depict uncorrelated patterns, the red lines denote well-matched patterns that are delivered to physical tests (solid) or to recycling area as defects. The graphic interpretation of the digital image convolution is shown at the right-hand side of the figure.

After image identification, the object diversion to the back-end physical-test platform for notch depth, battery capacity, and strain measurements is carried out with robotic-assisted Uarm Metal. The utilization of the ATmega168 chip and Arduino

Figure 7. Grey-scale images and graphic interpretations of image convolution of characteristic templates and objects.

IDE help realize the simultaneous control of three-axial motors in the Uarm and Bluetooth receiver and transmitter, and complete the diversion.

The control of the mechanical system of the platform was achieved with Arduino Uno combining pressure and voltage sensors. The measurement of the temperature- and tension-induced strains in terms of optical pulse deviation from fiber Bragg gratings provide an alternative for fragmental detection. In Fig.8 we show the variation of strain intensity with wavelength measured by the high performance optical spectrum analyzer, Agilent 86146B.

Figure 8. Temperature- and tension-induced strains on fiber gratings.

Figure 9. The notch depth meter on ThingSpeak.

Figure 10. The dynamic records of voltage and notch depth on ThingSpeak.

Completion checklist and feedback

Completion checklist

- Notch depth
- Battery power
- Engine

Customer feedback

- 100%
- 80%
- 60%
- 40%
- 20%
- 0%
- Others: Excellent

Figure 11. The completion checklist and real-time customer feedback.

Finally, the test results in terms of notch depth meter (Fig. 9) and dynamic records (Fig. 10) were uploaded to the public cloud server, ThingSpeak, via the ESP-8266 Wi-Fi module to supply the service for information interaction and real-time customer feedback within the Google form (Fig. 11).

SUMMARY

Via the integration of embedded microcontroller utilities and physical sensing environments, this project successfully demonstrates in the laboratory the kernel of Industry 4.0 in customized smart detection and the Internet of things through front-end objective identification, back-end physical properties measurement, and a cloud-supplied information platform and stimulate interdisciplinary collaboration between science and engineering for physics undergraduates.

From the perspective of engineering technique, the connection of the practical mechanical system and the platform of information interaction demonstrate the paradigm of a cyber-physical system. From the perspective of engineering education, the project-oriented training provides the opportunity for students to experience the practical operation, difficulties, and the need in maintaining a factory. Therefore, this provides the opportunity for students of science and engineering to work together and to stimulate new ideas and imagination to propose feasible solutions and suggestions to help improve the reliability and efficiency of the production and the manufacture. By means of the image identification, physical tests, and cloud interactions, our project has successfully demonstrated the idea and operating processes to approach the dream of smart factory.

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